

INFLUENCE OF PARENTING STYLES AND PARENTS' EDUCATIONAL LEVEL ON SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

Early studies proposed that parents are in charge of their children's emotional and social development and that a child's home environment shapes certain attitudes in him that are aided or hampered by his experiences at school. In today's world, a lot of the good attitudes that parents teach their children at home are hampered by some of the experiences they have outside of the family and at school. As a result, these experiences lead to youngsters having more trouble in school and adjusting to their social environment. The study applied the ex-post facto design. Students involved in the study include 368 senior secondary school students. The questionnaire served as the primary tool for data gathering. One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the t-test were used to evaluate the generated data. The results showed that parental styles have a substantial impact on their children's social adjustment, whereas parents' educational backgrounds had no significant impact on their children's social adjustment in the state. This study would be beneficial to parents, teachers and students. Based on the findings it will enlighten parents, students and teachers that parental styles and parental educational level greatly influence children social adjustment.

Keywords:

Parenting styles, Parents' educational level, Social Adjustment, Secondary School Students, Secondary School

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Introduction

Early studies proposed that parents are in charge of their children's emotional and social development and that a child's home environment shapes certain attitudes in him that are aided or hampered by his experiences at school. The behaviour patterns of older children and teenagers are a joint responsibility of parents and school personnel or instructors. However, in today's world, a lot of the good attitudes that parents teach their children at home are hampered by some of the experiences they have outside of the family and at school. As a result, these experiences lead to youngsters having more trouble in school and adjusting to their social environment. According to DeRosier and Lloyd (2012), parental education level is a significant predictor of the educational and behavioral outcomes of children. The measure of the parents' education often indicates whether or not the parents of the child or student attended secondary schools or other higher levels of education. In a formal learning environment, a child's family history is an important tool, and the educational factors of their parents have a significant impact on their academic achievement and adjustment. When we look at family differences in terms of parents' occupations, levels of education, money, and family status, we can see that parents' levels of education impact their children's academic achievement and behaviour (Odofin, 2020).

Child-rearing strategies inside social groups are socialisation procedures that exert a substantial influence on a child's moral judgement and social development. Children raised in such households have accelerated moral development and consistently demonstrate moral behaviour as they progress in nurturing, affectionate, polite, aesthetically pleasing, and tranquil social settings. According to Sharma (2012), behavioural issues among young people in Nigeria, such as hooliganism or criminality, are on the rise. It is a manifestation of behaviours that are at odds with the norms and standards set by the schools and that hinder young people's progress, academic success, social development, and overall growth. This behaviour disturbs other people, obstructs society's and schools' regular operations, and makes a nuisance of itself. The factors of children's immoral behaviour are discussed by Obeh (2009). He claims that the majority of youngsters that exhibit antisocial and deviant behaviour originate from dysfunctional households with strained relationships and a lack of parental love and compassion. He adds that people openly show criminal inclinations, mistreat one another with malice, and show no regard for societal norms and values. Children in these families and society as a whole witness constant arguments, physical fights, and violence. All of these issues may be the result of the parents' lack of knowledge or education, which rendered them unprepared to raise their kids in a way that promoted healthy emotional and social growth. Parents who neglect to instil in their children the essential social skills and ethical conduct required for successful engagement with society inadvertently expose their children to increased susceptibility to deviant and antisocial behaviours perpetrated by individuals seeking to exploit them, including indiscipline (Ozuri&Odofin, 2021).

Adults in Nigerian society, according to Obeh (2009), should be cognizant of the fact that a society devoid of insecurity and animosity is more likely to exist in settings where people are interested in and understand one another, where marital relationships are positive and peaceful, and where children are taught to emulate good behaviour. He continues by stating that the "leaders of tomorrow" will have an easier time adjusting to social situations at home and school if teachers set a good example by acting morally themselves. This will make it harder for them to suddenly stray from those high standards. Akiboh (2009) states that Nigeria faces a similar problem, where the lack of restrictions on extramarital activities, an increase in single parenthood, and a decrease in parental responsibilities have caused the family to become less important, with some of its traditional roles being undermined.

All of these aforementioned factors have an influence on the moral and social development of young children.

The concept of adjustment has been inherent in human existence from ancient times, commencing at birth and concluding with death (Egbule, Okoh&Eluowa, 2022). The term "adjustment" is widely used, and life is an ongoing process of adaptation. In simpler terms, individuals engage in various activities such as eating, drinking, sleeping, relaxing, seeking affection, striving for social interaction, working to meet economic demands, chasing independence, or fulfilling personal needs (Egbule et al., 2022). There are wants that one strives to satisfy, said Egbule et al. Unmet needs cause stress and make people agitated, hostile, disobedient, impolite, criminal, unsocialized, obsessive, grumpy, and unpleasant. These characteristics signify maladjustment. According to Egbule et al. (2022), a person having trouble meeting his demands is trying to adjust. Odojin and Ugoji (2023) assert that adolescents who are traumatized during childhood and adolescence show a low level of social competence and acceptance, tend to be isolated and rejected, and generally have worse relationships with others.

Even more, everyone can adjust; it is a dynamic idea. A condition of adjustment is one in which one aspires to be successful or content. As a result, one might change friends, romantic relationships, jobs, schools, and even themselves (Egbule et al., 2022). Therefore, social adjustment includes various elements, including the capacity for interpersonal interaction, the capacity for social participation, and the capacity for social norms, values, and disciplinary compliance. Parents might offer the child their first social environment to foster mutual like, love, and affection between the kid and themselves or other people. The atmosphere of social interaction and emotional stability in the family affects how well children develop trust, self-confidence, and the capacity to express themselves. Kids need a family with attention, warmth, and helping behaviour for the best social development. Every youngster who grows up in a trusting and self-assured atmosphere will have confidence in classmates and instructors (Basu, 2012). If they are to meet the social and intellectual demands of school life, children raised by antagonistic and argumentative parents will often require additional and special care at school (Basu, 2012). There have been numerous studies on the effects of families on students' general academic performance and other behaviours, but there have been fewer studies on the impact of parenting practices and parental education on students' social adjustment; hence, this study.

Research Hypotheses

- i. There exists no noteworthy disparity between students brought up under autocratic, democratic or permissive parenting styles in a social adjustment test.
- ii. There exists no noteworthy distinction between students from parents with high and low educational levels in a social adjustment test.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Adjustment

"Adaptation" is defined as "a change in behaviour or thought pattern," according to the seventh edition of the Oxford Advanced Learners' Current English Wordbook. adaptability was described as the capacity to handle social circumstances and meet one's needs by Aiken and Gary (2006), who examined the social attachment of adaptability. From a social perspective, Bhatia (2003) explains that adaptation entails adjusting to both the physical environment and societal expectations. According to Bhatia (2003), no living being can subsist solely on the resources provided by its physical environment. He asserts that the individual and his environment are linked through a series of actions and responses. Demands for socialisation and societal pressures are other factors. In addition to this,

there may be individualised needs that are comparable to meeting physiological demands. And because of how the human is complexly wired, adapting is essential.

Stella (2019) states that when people are able to adapt to their surroundings, it's because they've established a mutually beneficial relationship. There are two things that determine the level of harmony, say the authors:

- (i) Certain potentialities within a person and
- (ii) Character of the environment.

They explained that an individual is "adjusted" when connected to an adequate environment that makes them happy and productive and has some social feelings. They noted that adaptation is an all-encompassing term that denotes to the connection between a person and their environment. But, according to Mangal (2005), adaptation is a continuous process where a person changes their behavior to create a better relationship between themselves and their environment. Shaffer also talked about adaptation in the context of the need satisfaction process, saying that it's the process of a living organism finding a balance between their needs/necessities and the conditions that affect their satisfaction.

In his work, Denga (2002) categorises adjustment into three distinct groups, outlining the following categories:

- i. Social adjustment refers to how an individual can maintain a normal relationship with others. This includes family, friends, teachers and society.
- ii. One type of adjustment is educational adjustment, which measures how well a kid fits in at school and how well the academic programs and courses meet his needs. The child's feelings about the school and its surroundings might be either enthusiastic and positive or disinterested and unfavorable. Poor academic results are indicative of a learning disability.
- iii. Adjustment on an emotional or psychological level is focused on mood. Emotional or psychological maladjustment is characterized by emotional distress or psychological difficulties.

Denga (2002) concluded that several agencies must work together to adjust. According to Li and Zeng (2018), each of the following agencies must collaborate with others to carry out its particular tasks. The family, a child guidance center, the Boys' and Girls' Scouts, religious organizations, mental health organizations, theatrical clubs, goodwill organizations (charitable organizations), the Art Museum, the talented organization, and recreation centers are some of these organizations. Other scientists define it this way: how well a person's personality works in the world around them. It's about how well they fit in with their environment. It's the connection between the body, the environment, and the personality. They say that a well-adjusted person is well-equipped to do the job they're supposed to do in their situation. Their needs will be taken care of in line with the requirements of society. In 2003, Anyebe defined it this way: "Adjustment means harmony, conformity, or a good fit between a person and the standards they're judged by."

Concept of Social Adjustment

According to Anyebe (2003), social adjustment concerns how well a person maintains a harmonious relationship with others. It also concerns how they deal with their family, friends, teachers, and others. According to Hurluck, quoted by Li and Zeng (2018), social adjustment refers to a person's success in adjusting to other individuals and the group with which he is affiliated. She continued by saying that a well-adjusted person has mastered the ability to negotiate with friends and strangers so that they will view him favorably and wish to welcome him. She said the guy had an excellent social attitude and

was prepared to help others, even if it inconvenienced him. Li and Zeng (2018) outlined four (4) requirements for a well-adjusted individual to meet to be considered socially adjusted. These are:

- i. Overt performance
- ii. Adjustment to any group
- iii. Social attitudes
- iv. Personal Satisfaction

According to Obegh (2009), social adjustment refers to how well individuals get along at work, family, and school. A vital and significant social adjustment in life is how one adapts to their group. According to Egbule and Egbule (2008), a person with good social skills knows how to interact politely with friends, supervisors, guests, and co-workers so that others have positive and friendly views toward them. One of the most effective methods of social adjustment is the willingness to help others, even at one's inconvenience. According to Bhatia's explanation in 2003, the family's socioeconomic situation significantly impacts the child's personality. The possibility that the needs of the children will be fulfilled sufficiently and that they will adjust well is higher if the family's socioeconomic situation is favorable. However, suppose the family's socioeconomic circumstances are not encouraging or favorable. In that case, the children's needs won't be effectively and fully satisfied, and they'll start to feel inferior and insecure, which might harm their mental health. Mangal (2005) agreed with Bhatia's 2003 thoughts that the family's financial situation affects how well youngsters adjust. He says:

"The family's financial situation significantly impacts the child's personality. Children's requirements will be properly fulfilled and adjusted appropriately if the family's financial situation is sound. The requirements of the children will not be adequately satisfied if, on the other hand, the family's financial situation is poor, and the children will grow up with a sense of inferiority and insecurity that might harm their mental health (Adjustment)."

According to Li and Zeng's (2018) research, both students and instructors see parental economic status as contributing to student dropout rates. They said that the study was in line with that of Michael (2008), who claimed that poor socioeconomic position creates settings unfavorable for good adolescent adjustment, resulting in problem behaviour like dropout. Sharma (2012) concluded that the social adaptations of students from low and high socioeconomic statuses were considerably different. Although children from small and medium-sized households sometimes experience sibling rivalries and jealousies, parental over-protection, and accusations of favoritism, Stella (2019) asserts that these kids usually adjust to life better and are happier than kids from large families. According to her, small-family children are more likely to experience democratic child-raising, which helps them develop traits important for successful leadership and social adjustment.

As to the findings of Sutherland, Conroy and McLeod (2019), individuals who are bright tend to be well regarded and respected by their parents, teachers, and classmates. These attributes empower individuals to utilise their cognitive abilities in order to create beneficial personal and societal adaptations. They have an affinity with individuals. Typically, they possess high levels of vitality, autonomy, ingenuity, resourcefulness, assertiveness, cooperation, humour, dependability, self-assurance, and responsiveness to the opinions of others. According to Stella (2019), those with high intellect in maturity exhibit superior personal and social adaptability compared to those with medium intelligence. Research indicates that individuals with high intelligence possess traits such as

introspective thinking, thoughtfulness, creativity, and a sense of adventure. They are deeply interested in matters related to concerns, meanings, and values, and exhibit a wide range of interests, particularly in theoretical and aesthetic domains, in which they excel. Their heightened cognitive ability grants them superior self-regulation.

Weiss, Muckenthaler and Kiel (2020) proposed that working-class boys exhibited enhanced social adaptability when their mothers were worked, regardless of whether they belonged to one-parent or two-parent families. Despite the middle-class boys' advanced academic results, there was little evidence to support the notion that their fathers' profession provided them with social adaptation benefits. The author also elucidates that previous investigations have identified certain social adjustment disparities between children with employed and unemployed mothers, albeit with reduced magnitude. He clarified that the children of working parents have been encouraged to develop greater independence, especially when interacting with their peers in academic environments, and to get higher scores on tests of socio-emotional adjustment. The outcomes for boys have exhibited a moderate level of inconsistency and differ according to social class and the age at which the children were assessed.

Weiss et al.'s (2020) conclusion that adolescents with working mothers got less attention than students in the past whose mothers were not working was supported to some extent by Kumar (2013). He continued by saying that working mothers in nuclear families rely more on servants and childcare facilities for their children's development because they are unable to balance their demands for education and recreation with the stress of their jobs, which has an adverse effect on the kids' mental and physical health. Nevertheless, it is commonly observed that in extended families, there is an inadequate allocation of duties and privileges for each individual nuclear family, which can impact the student's adaptation. In households with many generations living together, the dynamics can vary due to the larger number of family members and the distribution of responsibilities among them, which can be advantageous for women who are employed. According to Margetts (2013), parents' socioeconomic position and occupational status affect how their kids acclimate to school. Margetts discovered that externalizing behaviour, hyperactivity, and general problem conduct were substantially related to attending before-school care. This prediction of poor adjustment results warrants additional research; nevertheless, he claims that this was due to the fact that some of the children in his study attended before-school care.

Parents' Education and Social Adjustment

Studies on parenting have found that parent education is linked to a nurturing and sociable environment inside the household, as indicated by Davis-Kean (2005) and Good and Hillary (2019). They hypothesised that the level of parental warmth could be accurately determined just based on the mother's level of education. However, they found that both the mother's education and the family's money were important factors in predicting the quality of the home's physical environment and the learning experiences provided. In addition, Smith et al., cited by Davis-Kean, found that the home environment played a role in moderating the connection between family income, parental education, and children's academic achievement. The mediation effect was more prominent for maternal education as compared to family income. Hence, these authors postulated that specific behaviours associated with accomplishment within the household, such as reading, engaging in play, and participating in other activities, could potentially have a correlation with academic performance. Davis-Kean (2005) as cited in Egbule and Egbule (2008) found that mother's education had a consistently good direct influence on children's cognitive and behavioural results, along with some indirect impacts from a mentally stimulating home environment. According to Dubow et al. (2009),

parental education is a significant indicator of socioeconomic level and, as previously said, affects children's academic and behavioural results.

According to Good and Hillary (2019), students with higher grades often also achieved higher mean scores on personality tests, indicating more successful personal adjustment. Mueller concluded that more adaptability and emotional stability are related to higher intellectual capacity. According to Laursen's (2005) theory, kids who experience parental abandonment, severe discipline, or neglect are more likely to develop self-defeating coping mechanisms. The development of non-constructive forms of coping is also influenced by repeated failure at school or continuous rejection in the peer culture.

Social Adjustment and its Impact on Learning

According to Love and Thomas (2014), most parents know that a child's happiness and social adjustment are closely related. Middle-class parents are particularly worried because they are focused on the future. Parents believe that if parents are liked by both boys and girls and start to create social activities with people of both sexes before childhood ends, their children will be happy. They go on to say that even instructors in the present day are more concerned about behaviour that promotes poor adjustment than behaviour that interferes with the orderly operation of the classroom. Most educators know from their classrooms that kids with high social skills typically perform better academically.

The sort of social adjustments the youngster makes also impacts his self-concepts, according to Love and Thomas (2014). This also helps to explain why it persists. A socially adaptable youngster grows to have a positive self-image; if other people like him, he will also like himself. She came to the conclusion that the emphasis placed on childhood adjustment is appropriate, considering the persistence of the behaviours and attitudes formed and accepted during that period. This is since any behaviour that results in a youngster receiving social acceptance is repeated and quickly develops into a habit. According to Seginer and Mahajna (2018), mental health, particularly adjustment, helps education through promoting learning and enhancing the learning environment rather than engaging in particular activities or objectives.

Concept of Parenting Style

Most parents are consistently concerned about the achievement of their children. The majority of parents desire to facilitate their children's pursuit of various interests, be it in academics, the arts, athletics, or other domains. An optimal method to accomplish this is by acknowledging that parents are exposed to a multitude of theories. Certain parents deliberately endeavour to ensure their children's success, while others find it advantageous to adopt a more relaxed attitude. It's critical to comprehend the distinction between parenting practices and parenting styles, according to Aldhafri et al. (2020).

Turner et al. (2009) states that parents' practises are the actions they take to help their children develop social skills. For instance, if parents want their kids to do well in school, they might set an example by sitting down with them and helping them with their homework, allocating time for homework and reading, or prioritizing their kids' education by attending events like parent-teacher conferences. As Stella (2019) quoted, Darling and Steinberge describe a parenting style as the emotional environment in which parents raise their children. According to Aldhafri et al. (2020), parental attentiveness and demandingness are two factors that define parenting styles.

Rebeiro (2009) coined the term "parenting styles" to refer to the ways in which parents interact with

their children during the process of socialisation. According to the author, a significant portion of the study on parenting styles has concentrated on the three specific parenting philosophies categorised by Aldhafri et al. (2020) as authoritarian, authoritative (Democratic), and permissive. According to several experts, such as Aldhafri et al., the permissive style of parenting can be divided into two distinct philosophies: permissive indulgent and permissive indifferent (also referred to as permissive rejecting, permissive neglecting, and presently uninvolved parenting). Research conducted by Birina (2017) has shown that a child's philosophical perspective has a direct impact on their ability to learn effectively. A child's home environment, including the parenting style employed there, is one aspect that may have an impact on the child's psychological health and subsequent development (Maria, 2018). The concept of parenting style is required to account for the typical variances in parental attempts to discipline and socialize their children (Maria, 2018). It encompasses two crucial facets of parenting, viz dependability and responsiveness of parents (Hadia&Seema, 2013).

Parental responsiveness, sometimes referred to as parental warmth or supportiveness, refers to the extent to which parents actively encourage individuality, self-control, and self-expression by being attentive, accommodating, and sensitive to their children's specific needs and requests (Birina, 2017). Parental demandingness, also known as behavioural control, pertains to the expectations parents have regarding their children's ability to assimilate into the family and society as a whole. This includes their requirements for maturity, supervision, disciplinary actions, and willingness to address defiant behaviour in their children (Okwaraji et al., 2016).

Types of Parenting Styles

- **Authoritarian parent** - when a child's actions or beliefs go against what the authoritative parent believes to be proper conduct, she (the parent) values obedience as a virtue and favors her own will. Authoritarian parents make an effort to mold, control, and evaluate the child's behavior and attitudes per a standard of conduct, which is typically an absolute standard. She thinks the best way to instill respect for labor is to keep the youngster in place, limit his autonomy, and give him domestic tasks.
- **Authoritative (Democratic) parent** - According to Grobman (2003), an authoritative (Democratic) parent makes an effort to control their child's behavior, but in a logical, issue-focused way. She (the parent) promotes vocal concessions and demands, explains her policy to the youngster and begs for his objections when he defies it. She, therefore, exercises rigorous control at the point when parent and child interests split but does not confine the kid. To accomplish her goals, she uses authority, reason, and regime and enforcement molding rather than group consensus or the wants of the particular kid.
- **Permissive parent** - A permissive parent adopts a non-punitive approach, embracing and supporting the child's inclinations, wishes, and behaviours. The parent seeks the child's input and provides explanations before finalising family policies. She imposes few constraints on behaviour or household responsibilities. She presents herself to the child as a mere instrument that he can manipulate according to his desires, rather than serving as a role model for him to emulate or as an influential factor in moulding or altering his current or future conduct. She refrains from exercising dominion over him and dissuades him from conforming to regulations imposed by others, granting him as much autonomy as feasible to oversee his own pursuits (Li, 2019).

According to Nwabuike and Nwankwo (2020), there are four types of parenting styles: authoritarian, authoritative (Democratic), neglectful, and indulgent, with authoritative (Democratic) parenting - which combines warmth, verbal compromise, and some limit setting - being the best. Being both demanding and responsive, authoritative parents keep

an eye on their kids' behaviour and have a positive influence on it. (Ukokal, 2007) discovered that father-mother cooperation and mutual respect allow children to develop good views. They are assertive without being invasive or restricting.

Methodology

The researcher used ex-post facto study design. Students from public senior secondary schools in Delta State's 25 local government area councils comprised the study's population. The estimated population is 52,783 (fifty-two thousand, seven hundred and eighty-three). In choosing the schools and the participants, the researcher employed stratified and proportional random sampling approaches, respectively. This is so because, according to Umar (2013), the stratified sampling is a frequently employed probability sampling strategy that is preferable to random sampling since it lowers sampling error. This approach generated 368 senior secondary school students as the sample size for the study. Questionnaires were the instruments utilized to gather the data. When the instrument was delivered to professionals in guidance and counseling, the study used the instrument face and content validity to determine its utility. The first hypothesis, which likewise aims to ascertain the differences in mean social adjustment test scores of kids raised under autocratic, democratic, or permissive parenting styles, was tested using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The second hypothesis, which compares the mean social adjustment test scores of children of highly and less educated parents and male and female students, is tested using the T-test.

Results

Hypothesis I

There exists no noteworthy disparity between students brought up under autocratic, democratic or permissive parenting styles in a social adjustment test.

Table 1: Test of Social Adjustment of Students from Three (3) Parenting Styles

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std	Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Error	
Autocratic	368	14.00	68.00	15800.00	40.3204	.35167	6.84858
Democratic	368	16.00	70.00	17878.00	47.7660	.36571	6.89434
Permissive	368	15.00	60.00	10517.00	29.2087	.40358	7.83163

The distribution of respondents' statistical responses, together with mean scores and standard deviations, are displayed in the table above. According to table 1, for the effect of parenting approaches on social adjustment were 47.76 for democratic, 40.32 for autocratic, and 29.20 for permissive, correspondingly.

Table 2: One-way ANOVA Comparison of Social Adjustment of students brought up under the three (3) different parenting styles.

Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	Prob.
Between groups	23	166.874	2.143	.000
Within groups	344	39.628		

The F-ratio is (2.143), at the threshold of significance 0.05 and 344 df 23. The F-ratio values (2.143) are less than the crucial threshold (3.05). P (.000) has a probability level of significance lower than 0.05. As a result, the null hypothesis, which indicated that parenting style impacted senior secondary school students' social adjustment in Delta State, is rejected. The conclusion was that parenting practices significantly impact how well students adjust to social situations, with democratic parenting practices having the highest (47.76). As determined by the one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with 23/344 degrees of freedom, the computed F-ratio of 2.143 was significant at 0.05 level of probability. This indicates that there are considerable disparities between pupils who were raised in authoritarian, democratic, or permissive parental environments. The null hypothesis was rejected in light of this finding, demonstrating that parental practices considerably impact how well students adjust to their social environment.

Hypothesis 2

There exists no noteworthy distinction between students from parents with high and low educational levels in a social adjustment test.

Table 3: T-test showing the Social Adjustment of Students from Parents with Low and High Educational Level

Educational level	N	Mean	S.D	T-cal	D f	Pro b.
Low	25 3	36.447 3	4.5648	.32 5	3 6 6	.102
High	11 6	36.641 6	5.3132			
Total	36 7					

The t-test mentioned above reveals that the social adjustment for students whose parents had high and low educational qualifications were 36.64 and 36.44, respectively. The t-test result also reveals that the t-calculated value (.325) is below the t-critical value (1.96) at 0.05 significant level, and the probability level of significance P(.102) is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the social adjustment of students from parents with high and low educational levels is not significantly different. The null hypothesis is thus maintained, demonstrating that parents' educational level has no impact on how well kids adjust socially.

Discussion of Findings

The outcome of this study's assessment of hypothesis one (1) reveals that parental practices significantly impact how well students adjust to their social environment. Additionally, it demonstrated how parental discipline, control, support, and other forms of love and affection impact students' patterns of social adjustment. Students from within and across cultures are exposed to the possibility of situational issues that evident in problem behavior, including aggression, stealing, assault, destruction of school property (school rioting), and rape, as well as examination fraud, intra-group fighting, and cultism (Denga, 2002).

In most instances, psychological factors are the underlying potential causes of these problematic behaviors. The socio-psychological makeup of a person includes how he interacts with his surroundings, especially the household where his parents are in charge. The study's findings and those of Unete et al. (2010) are in agreement with each other. Additionally, the results are consistent with Isangedigi's (2007) theory that a kid has to gain self-confidence, trust, and personal expression to engage in healthy social development. He believes this depends on the social climate his parents have created at home. He believes adopting a healthy parenting style is the only way to provide children with the warmth, affection, and helpful conduct they need.

The finding of this study's second hypothesis, "There is no significant difference between the students from parents with high and how educational level in social adjustment test," showed that parental education does not necessarily affect social adjustment. Even if it succeeds in another setting, it might not be feasible. The results of hypothesis two contradict the findings of Durbow et al. (2009), who highlighted that parental education impacts behavioral adjustment and educational (academic) and occupational performance.

CONCLUSION

The study's findings led the researchers to conclude that parents' parenting practices substantially impact how well their children adjust socially. This is a sign that parents must comply with the updated rules regarding their interactions with their wards. Additionally, the study provided evidence of the value of democracy in general leadership and treatment since adolescents from democratically inclined parents exhibited socially cognizant behavior.

RECOMMENDATION

- i. Parents should make an effort to adopt a parenting style, such as the democratic parenting style, as parenting practices have an impact on kids' social adjustment. This style ensures or guarantees that students will acquire positive self-concept, self-confidence, and self-esteem.
- ii. In this classroom management, teachers should be encouraged to utilize a democratic type of punishment. This is because the teaching method promotes dialogue and give-and-take, which the study found to be better for students' social and personal development, and parents, instructors, and counselors should be in frequent contact with both students and their parents. The communication lines must never break to prevent loss of control and monitoring, which results in pupils' social maladjustment.
- iii. Parents, professors, and students should inspire them to strive for better success than their own. They could learn effective social adjustment behaviors as a result of this.

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